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ABCC5 functions in multi-drug resistance in human cancer in metastasis to the bone.

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We describe here a function for the ATP-binding cassette gene *ABCC5* in multi-drug resistance in human cancer (1-3), supported by evidence by demonstrating its transcriptional up-regulation with significance at the transcriptome level in metastasis to distant organ sites in human breast cancer (4, 5), and by separate evidence demonstrating that ATP-binding cassette genes function in multi-drug resistance: in resistance to a platinum agent, in resistance to doxorubicin, and in resistance to paclitaxel (2).

Results

Figure 1: ABCC5 is differentially expressed in the bone metastases of humans with breast cancer.

I. Metastasis to the bone in humans with breast cancer.

n=3 MCF7 (human; breast cancer)

n=3 MCF7b bone metastatic variant

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
10057	1.38E-05	0.0539	-4.346799	-0.2342031	4147.88	ABCC5	5577/20047	72.2

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in human breast cancer cells (MCF7) and a metastatic MCF7 variant, MCF7b, we discovered differential expression of ATP binding cassette subfamily C member 5, encoded by *ABCC5* in metastasis to the bone in breast cancer (**Chart 1**). The expression of *ABCC5* changed more than 70% of the human breast cancer transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 20,047 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of *ABCC5* messenger RNA in breast cancer bone metastasis, demonstrating up-regulation of *ABCC5* during disease progression and metastasis.

II. Metastasis to the bone in humans with breast cancer.

n=3 normal mammary epithelial cells (human)

n=3 metastasis to the bone (human; TNBC)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
ILMN_1651964	5.16E-10	-32.075032	13.87948	-2.5793187	ABCC5	467/40614	98.9

Through comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of humans with breast cancer as compared to metastasis to the bone, we validated differential expression and transcriptional induction of *ABCC5* in bone metastasis in humans (**Chart 2**). The expression of *ABCC5* here changed more than 98% of the breast cancer transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 40,614 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of *ABCC5* messenger RNA in the bone metastases of humans with breast cancer, demonstrating up-regulation of *ABCC5* during transformation and disease progression.

Thus, differential and increased expression of *ABCC5* defines the bone metastatic tumor transcriptome in human breast cancer.

Discussion

We described here transcriptional induction of a gene with functions in multi-drug resistance, in bone metastasis in human breast cancer. Novel approaches to challenging metastasis and resistance will utilize chemotherapy in conjunction with i) kinase and phosphatase inhibitors targeted to tissue and tumor type whose functions overlap with that of growth factor and growth factor receptor inhibitors, ii) inhibitors of the ATP-binding cassette family (multi-drug resistance pumps), and iii) CDK4/6 inhibitors, which function as senescence-inducing agents.

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Methods

We measured total transcription in primary tumors and metastasis to distant organ sites including the bones, the brain, the liver and the lungs using microarray and RNA-sequencing datasets (GSEXXXXX and GSEXXXXX) and R-based computational software for exact quantitative determination of multi-drug resistant pump transcriptional induction at the transcriptome level.